

Separation of Th(IV) in Aqueous Glycine Medium by Cation Exchange Chromatography

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Through cation exchange column chromatography using Dowex 50W-X8 (Na⁺ form, 100-200 mesh) in aqueous 0.20 M glycine media, analytical conditions predicted from the distribution coefficient (*K*), have enabled the separation of a wide concentration of Th(IV) from U(VI), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), La(III), Ce(III), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pb(II), Ag(I), Cu(II) or Hg(II). The following ternary mixtures were also resolved: Th(IV)-Cu(II)/Hg(II)-U(VI)/Al(III)/Cr(III)/Fe(III)/La(III)/Ce(III)/Ca(II)/Sr(II)/Ba(II)/Mn(II)/Co(II)/Ni(II)/Zn(II)/Cd(II)/Pb(II)/Ag(I). In all the separations column kinetics was found to be favourable, though the separation of Th(IV) was almost but not quite quantitative. Values of *K*, elution characteristics of metal ions, elution curves and results of the resolution of a number of mixtures are presented.

MOST of the reported methods⁷ for the separation of thorium by ion exchange in HCl, HNO₃ or H₂SO₄ media suffer from disadvantages rendering the resolution of mixtures containing a number of metal ions difficult. The slow kinetics of ion exchange in the mineral acids is perhaps a serious drawback, which results in tailing in the chromatograms. For example, anion exchange chromatography in 5-6 M HNO₃ is highly selective for Th(IV)^{1,2} but tailing of U(VI) and a few other metal ions limits the application of this method. Considerably better kinetics, though not excellent, was obtained in 0.60 M HNO₃ containing 55% acetone^{7,8}. Also, in the case of cation exchange separations of Th(IV), eluting agents such as 3 M H₂SO₄^{9,12} or 0.50 M oxalic acid¹¹ are inefficient because kinetics is slow and for the quantitative recovery of Th(IV), the resin must be ignited to ash^{14,15,16} and Th(IV) determined in the residue. However, Strelow *et al*¹⁷ were able to devise a method for the separation of Th(IV), which does not require ashing.

Glycine is a versatile complexant¹⁸ and among the separations described using glycine, are those of Zn(II)-Cd(II)^{9,22} and of Cu(II)-Co(II)⁴. A chelating exchanger was used by Hering⁵ for studying the ion exchange behaviours of Fe(III), Cu(II), Ni(II), Co(II), Mg(II) and K(I). Glycine and other amino acids along with other complexants were used as retaining agents for the separation of several less familiar elements on NH₄⁺-form nuclear sulphonic acid exchanger at 85-90°C²¹. Jercan and Dinou⁶ reported the concentration and separation of U(VI) from diverse ions using Dowex 2X-8 and Vionite AT-1 anion exchanger in glycine (pH > 3.4 to < 6) solution containing α,α'-bipyridyl.

In this work, a systematic study has been done on the possibility of concentration and separation of Th(IV) in aqueous glycine medium. The

following metal ions, U(VI), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(III), La(III), Ce(III), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Hg(II), Pb(II) and Ag(I) were also studied for obtaining the analytical conditions under which Th(IV) may be separated from mixtures. The resin used was strongly acidic Dowex 50W-X8. On the basis of the *K* values, specific separation of Th(IV) from 18 other metal ions was achieved by column chromatography. A wide range of concentrations of glycine and Th(IV) were studied for the separation but only one typical set is included here. Better recovery of Th(IV) occurs when glycine is below 0.4 M, while the recovery shows a fall if the concentration of glycine is higher. *K* values, elution behaviour of metal ions, elution curves and results of the resolution of various mixtures are reported in this communication.

Experimental

Material :

(a) *Water* : De-ionised distilled water was used in all the experiments.

(b) *Metal ion solution* : Aqueous 0.06-0.20 M solutions of U(VI), Al(III), Cr(III), La(III), Ca(II), Sr(II), Ba(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pb(II) and Ag(I) were prepared from reagent grade nitrate samples (BDH AnalaR or Johnson Mathey). Solutions of Hg(II), 0.10 M in 0.10 M glycine, and of Th(IV), 0.05 M in 0.05 M glycine were prepared from their nitrate samples (BDH AnalaR) directly in glycine solution. Fe(III) solution, 0.06 M in 0.06 M glycine was prepared from ammonium iron(III) sulphate directly in aqueous glycine solution. Cerous chloride (Johnson Mathey) was used to prepare aqueous solution of Ce(III). The solutions were standardised by determining the metal contents^{5,19,20}.

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(c) *Glycine solution* : 2.0 M stock solution of glycine (E. Merck, G.R.) was prepared in water. Freshly prepared solutions were used.

(d) *Ion exchange resin* : Strongly acidic polystyrene based sulphonic acid Dowex 59W-X8 (Na⁺-form, 100-200 mesh) was washed in a column with ca 0.2 M EDTA solution (pH 8-10) and then with water. The resin in the Na⁺-form was obtained by passing a large excess of ca 10% NaCl solution through the column and then washing with water until free from chloride ions. The resin in the Na⁺-form was air dried on a sintered bed by applying suction and was stored in an air tight bottle. The capacity and water content were found to be 3.04 meq/g and about 21%, respectively.

Apparatus :

(a) *Equilibration studies* : A wrist motion micriod flask shaker (Griffin & George), operating on 220 V/50 cycles A.C. mains was used for shaking the solutions with the resin in 100 ml pyrex flasks.

(b) *pH measurements* : A Leeds and Northrup pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Distribution studies :

An appropriate amount of metal ion (about 30% of the total exchange capacity of resin) solution and aqueous glycine of the desired concentration (0.04 to 1.60M) were mixed and 1 g of resin was added. This was shaken for 1 hr and the resin was filtered off. The metal content was determined in the solution phase. Glycine did not interfere in the estimation of metal ions. *K* was determined using the relationship, $K = \text{meq metal per g of resin/meq metal per ml of solution}$.

All experiments were performed at least in duplicate, at $30 \pm 2^\circ$, and the average values are recorded (Table 1). The relative experimental error in the determination of *K* values was usually ± 5 to 10%.

Results and Discussion

In general, *K* values of most of the metal ions studied decrease with an increase in glycine concentration from 0.04 to 1.60 M (Table 1). Complexation with glycinate ion is, perhaps, the dominant factor which governs the trend and magnitude of the sorption. The cation exchange sorption of a metal ion decreases as the charge on the species formed changes from a small positive value to zero and finally becomes negative. Previous studies^{2,3} has confirmed that an effective decrease in the sorption is not necessarily accompanied by the formation of a negatively charged species.

Water molecules coordinated with metal ions are generally replaced by glycine as its concentration is increased, resulting in the formation of small positive charged or neutral species in most of the cases, leading to the decrease of *K* values. Further increase of glycine concentration perhaps favours the formation of neutral species as indicated by appreciably high values of *K*. The high values of *K* even at higher concentrations of glycine, in almost all metal ions except Th(IV), Cu(II) and Hg(II), suggest that metal ions or complex ions with a low charge have higher affinity for cation exchanger than glycine in aqueous medium.

Though Th (IV) has the highest positive charge amongst the metal ions, it shows the lowest affinity

TABLE 1—DISTRIBUTION COEFFICIENTS IN AQUEOUS GLYCINE

Metal Ion	Distribution coefficients (<i>K</i>)						
	Conc. of aqueous glycine (M)						
	0.04	0.12	0.20	0.40	0.64	1.00	1.60
Al(III)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)
Ca(II)	1290	1080	1060	1220	1290	1080	1220
Cr(III)	1620	1240	1800	2460	—	890	800
Mn(II)	2270	2530	2270	1970	1740	1890	1890
Fe(III)	2580	2010	1850	1150	670	560	480
Co(II)	3260	1820	2080	1200	680	420	270
Ni(II)	2600	1050	690	320	190	110	60
Cu(II)	340	90	49	28	8.8	4.9	2.2
Zn(II)	1040	950	760	560	400	310	240
Sr(II)	1720	1600	—	1410	—	—	4050
Ag(I)	280	280	280	260	240	200	170
Cd(II)	1250	1050	1050	1050	1050	780	780
Ba(II)	1120	1040	—	1690	—	—	2370
La(III)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)
Hg(II)	1690	230	80	25	12	6.0	3.4
Pb(II)	1440	1360	1360	1760	2750	8310	12400
Ce(III)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a) ²
Th(IV)	3.2	3.0	3.2	2.9	4.2	5.2	6.3
U(VI)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	630

a = Very high value.

for cation exchanger as the amount of glycine is increased. In the case of Cu(II) and Hg(II) the *K* values decrease appreciably with the increase in glycine concentration and at 1.60 *M* glycine the *K* values are even lower than that for Th(IV). This behaviour shown by Cu(II) and Hg(II) metal ions is due to their pronounced complexing tendency with glycine, resulting in the formation of perhaps negatively charged species¹⁰.

Prediction of separation possibilities :

K values suggest the utility of glycine for the separation of Th(IV) from other metal cations. Th(IV) should follow the feed effluent because of low affinity for the exchanger and other metal ions should be retained onto the resin bed due to higher affinity. The separation of Th(IV) from Cu(II) or

the column at the controlled flow rate of 1.0 ± 0.5 ml/min. Feed effluent was collected from the beginning of the sorption.

Elution : The sorption was followed by the quantitative elution of the components of the binary mixtures. The very weakly held Th(IV) was eluted with 40 ml of 0.20 *M* glycine (including 25 ml of feed effluent). The break-through of strongly sorbed other metal ions [except Cu(II) and Hg(II)] were not observed even after the passage of 125 ml of 1.0 *M* glycine (Table 2). Cu(II) or Hg(II) was recovered with 105 and 95 ml of 1.6 *M* glycine while other ions were stripped off with the help of other eluents. Al(III), Cr(III), Mn(II), Fe(III), Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Cd(II) and Ce(III) were eluted with about 80 ml of 2.5 *M* HCl, Ag(I) with 65 ml of 2.5 *M*

TABLE 2—ELUTION CHARACTERISTICS OF METAL IONS ON DOWEX 50W-X8 COLUMN

Metal	BTV(ml)	VEP (ml)	TEV (ml)	Eluting agent
Th(IV)	5	~20	40	0.20M Glycine
Cu(II)	15	45	105	1.6M Glycine
Hg(II)	5	30	95	—do—
Al(III)	> 125	—	—	2.5M HCl
Cr(III)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Fe(III)	> 125	—	—	—do—
La(III)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Ce(III)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Co(II)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Ni(II)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Zn(II)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Cd(II)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Mn(II)	> 125	—	—	—do—
Ca(II)	> 125	—	—	3M NH ₄ OAc
Sr(II)	> 125	—	—	2M NH ₄ OAc
Ba(II)	> 125	—	—	4M NH ₄ OAc
U(VI)	> 125	—	—	1M NH ₄ OAc
Pb(II)	> 125	—	—	4M NH ₄ OAc
Ag(I)	> 125	—	—	2.5M HNO ₃

BTV = Breakthrough volume.

VEP = Volume elution peak.

TEV = Total elution volume.

Hg(II) is noteworthy, since these cannot be achieved at higher glycine concentrations (>0.64 *M*) because of almost identical *K* values. Below 0.64 *M* glycine, Th(IV) should follow the feed effluent and the strongly retained Cu(II) or Hg(II) may thereafter be removed with higher amounts of glycine.

Separation of binary and ternary mixture :

Column chromatographic separations of Th(IV) from other metal ions were achieved under the conditions predicted from batch experimentation. The following procedure was adopted :

Preparation and pretreatment of resin bed : The resin slurry (~5 g) was prepared in water from pre-purified and washed Na⁺-resin. It was transferred to the graduated column (~65 cm long with internal diameter ~0.85 cm). The height of the resin bed was about 8.0 cm. It was then treated with 0.10 *M* or 0.20 *M* glycine solution, as the case is.

Preparation of feed and sorption : The feed, 25 ml in 0.20 *M* glycine, was prepared in duplicate by mixing known amounts of Th(IV) and one of the other cations studied. The feed was passed through

TABLE 3—RESULTS OF THE SEPARATION OF Th(IV) FROM A NUMBER OF METAL IONS

Th(IV) taken = 59.17 mg

Other Metal Ions*	Taken mg	Number of Determinations	Recovery of Th (IV) in (%)
Ag(I)	56.63	6	96.20
Mn(II)	27.42	6	95.90
Co(II)	29.46	6	96.01
Ni(II)	27.80	6	96.10
Cu(II)	31.77	8	96.00
Zn(II)	32.84	6	96.20
Ca(II)	20.10	6	96.30
Cd(II)	56.76	6	96.04
Hg(II)	100.80	8	96.08
Pb(II)	104.63	8	96.16
Sr(II)	25.66	6	96.12
Ba(II)	63.59	6	96.20
La(III)	45.70	6	95.98
Ce(III)	32.07	6	96.04
Al(III)	8.97	6	96.15
Fe(III)	17.51	8	96.20
Cr(III)	17.19	6	96.06
U(VI)	120.17	6	96.06

*The recovery of these were ~100%.

HNO₃, Ca(II) with 75 ml of 3 M NH₄OAc and Pb(II) with 75 ml of 4.0 M NH₄OAc. The results of the separations are reported in Table 3.

Th(IV) can also be separated from other metal ions [except Cu(II) and Hg(II)] at higher concentration (>1.0 M) of glycine. But the recovery of Th(IV) has been found to be only about 80-85%. The recovery may be enhanced upto 96% if the separation is done at lower (<0.20 M) concentration of glycine and hence all separations were achieved in 0.20 M glycine. In all the separations column kinetics is highly favourable, the recovery is good but not quite quantitative perhaps due to very slow ligand exchange rates.

Elution curves: Figs. 1 and 2 represent the elution curves for the resolution of the following mixtures: Th(IV)-Fe(III)/Ce(III)/Pb(II) and Th(IV)-Cu(II)/Hg(II), respectively. The concentration is represented in terms of ml of 0.01 M EDTA. Volume of the effluent in the figures also include the volume passing out of the resin bed from the feed.

Fig. 1. Elution curves: Th(IV)-Fe(III)/Ce(III)/Pb(II).

Fig. 2. Elution curves: Th(IV)-Hg(II)/Cu(II).

The separation between Th(IV) and Cu(II) or Hg(II) along with other cations at lower glycine

concentration (0.04-0.20 M) and of these three from other cations at higher glycine concentration (1.0-1.6 M) indicated the possibility of a number of ternary separations: Al(III)/Ca(II)/Cr(III)/Mn(II)/Fe(III)/Co(II)/Ni(II)/Zn(II)/Sr(II)/Ag(I)/Cd(II)/Ba(II)/Pb(II)/U(VI)/La(III)/Ce(III)-Cu(II)/Hg(II)-Th(IV).

For chromatographic separations of ternary mixtures, the feed was prepared in 0.1 M glycine by mixing any three of the above mentioned cations. Th(IV) followed the feed effluent whereas other metal ions were held onto the resin bed with considerable variation in sorption. Recovery of Th(IV) was achieved with 0.10 M glycine. Th(IV) exhibits almost similar behaviour as in 0.20 M glycine because it has almost identical *K* values in 0.04 to 0.20 M glycine. After the complete elution of Th(IV), not too strongly held Cu(II) or Hg(II) was eluted with 1.60 M glycine and finally the most strongly retained metal ions were desorbed with HCl, HNO₃ or HN₄OAc, as the case may be.

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